

**A RESEARCH DISSERTATION ON
DENTAL CARIES, DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF
THE ENAMEL AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN 9-YEAR-
OLDS OF IGBOORA, IBARAPA CENTRAL LOCAL
GOVERNMENT AREA, OYO STATE.**

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TO

**DEPARTMENT OF PERIODONTOLOGY AND COMMUNITY DENTISTRY,
FACULTY OF DENTISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN, IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT OF THE AWARD OF BACHELOR
OF DENTAL SURGERY.**

5TH OF JULY, 2019.

CERTIFICATION

We certify that this study “Dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis in 9-year-olds of Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government Area, Oyo State” was carried out by:

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SUPERVISOR'S ATTESTATION

This is to attest that this research work was carried out by Group 1 2015 BDS Class on the topic titled “**DENTAL CARIES, DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF THE ENAMEL AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN 9 YEAR OLDS OF IGBOORA, IBARAPA CENTRAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OYO STATE.**” in partial fulfilment of the award of Bachelor of Dental Surgery, University of Ibadan. The research work was supervised by me.

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DEDICATION

We dedicate this body of work to science and humanity's continuous quest for knowledge. It is our hope the knowledge this research work provides will make the world a better place.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dental caries has been commonly defined as a disease process which causes the demineralisation of dental hard tissues by microbial activity. It is a preventable disease which can be reversed in its early stages. Enamel formation is a natural process in the body which can be affected by environmental and genetic factors resulting in enamel defects like dental fluorosis and developmental defects of the enamel (DDE).

Objective: This study assessed the prevalence and socio-demographic characteristics and relationship between dental caries, DDE and dental fluorosis amongst 9-year old children with a view to providing information that will aid the prevention and treatment of these oral health problems.

Materials and Methods: This study was a cross sectional study involving 378 participants in Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria. The research project was carried out in 3 phases that investigated the prevalence of dental caries, developmental defects of enamel and dental fluorosis and also the relationship between them among nine-year olds in Igbo-ora, Oyo State.

In Phase 1, dental examination for the presence of dental caries, DDE and dental fluorosis using the dmft/DMFT indices, modified DDE index and Dean's indices respectively was undertaken for 378 nine-year-olds. In Phase 2, 152 semi-structured questionnaire was administered to parent/guardian in order to collect data on socio-demographic characteristics, pregnancy history, delivery history, childhood illnesses, dietary practices and tooth cleaning. In Phase 3, a well labelled universal bottle comprising the identification number was used to collect a sample of drinking water from 378 participants which will be later assessed for fluoride concentration. Frequencies and means were generated. Chi square test was used to test the associations between categorical variables at ($p < 0.05$) and continuous variables respectively.

Result: The prevalence of dental caries, DDE and dental fluorosis were 3%, 41% and 40% respectively. There was no relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis among our study participants ($p = 0.716$), there was no relationship between dental caries and DDE ($p = 0.642$) but we found a relationship between DDE and dental fluorosis ($p < 0.05$). Fluoride toothpaste use, gender, exclusive breastfeeding, and infant/childhood diseases were not statistically significant predictors of DDE and dental fluorosis.

Conclusion: Enamel formation is a process that is susceptible to many biological influences. This study confirms a common hypothesis which states that in population where the prevalence of dental fluorosis is high, the prevalence of dental caries is low.

Keywords: Prevalence, Dental Caries, DDE, Dental Fluorosis, Igbo-ora.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

The WHO has defined health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis are oral health conditions that affect the overall health and wellbeing of an individual.

Developmental defects of the enamel (DDE) have been defined as disturbances in hard tissue matrices and their mineralization that arise during odontogenesis. According to their clinical appearances, DDEs have been classified as demarcated opacity, diffuse opacity or hypoplasia (Fédération Dentaire Internationale Working Group, 1992).

Developmental defects of the enamel can have a significant effect on aesthetics, tooth sensitivity, tooth wear and dentofacial abnormalities (Yadav *et al*, 2015) and have a negative impact on the children's daily performance (Vargas-Ferreira *et al*, 2011). DDEs have been regarded by some authors as the main risk factors for dental caries even though its nature has not been identified and its cause is not clear (Salanitri *et al*, 2013).

Several studies on the prevalence and severity of DDEs and associated risk factors have been undertaken in different parts of the world, but limited work in Nigeria has shown a range in prevalence of DDEs, from 11% reported for 4- to 16-year-olds (Orenuga *et al*, 2010) to 23% reported for 12-year-olds (Koleoso, 2004) residing in 0.15-1.41 ppm F areas (Gbadebo, 2012).

Dental caries (which can result from developmental defects of the enamel) is a disease process resulting in the demineralisation of dental hard tissues by microbial activity. It is a readily preventable disease and can be arrested or reversed in its early stages (Kidd *et al*, 1997).

Caries is a multifactorial disease with an interplay of many factors such as the host microflora, substrate (food), tooth susceptibility, time and host saliva. Many modifications of this interplay have evolved (Fitzgerald *et al*, 1986). One of such modifications considers saliva as a separate unit and involves addition of time factor (Krasse *et al*, 1982).

As food is consumed, bacteria metabolize fermentable carbohydrates, producing acids, which diffuse into the dental hard tissue, and demineralize the tooth enamel (Featherstone, 2008). Rehman *et al* found a strong correlation of dental caries with snacking in between meals and frequency of refined sugar intake (Rehman *et al*, 2008). Thus, frequent consumption of refined carbohydrate increases the susceptibility of an individual to developing dental caries.

In a study done in Lagos State, South-western Nigeria in 2003, it showed that approximately 18% of children had untreated tooth decay in their primary dentition. A 26.1% increase from the year 2000. About 12% of the decayed, extracted and filled teeth (deft) index was seen in decayed teeth in 2000 and 16.6% in 2003. Over the study period, the overall reduction in the prevalence of dental caries was 34.8% in the permanent dentition. The decline was larger among children aged 5-9 years (62.1%) and among females (75%) (Sofola *et al*, 2000).

Dental caries, a product of man's progress toward civilization, has a high morbidity potential (Ingle *et al.*, 2014). Untreated dental caries can result in frequent tooth pain and difficulty in eating and sleeping which can affect child growth and is also the main reason of absence from school even in developed countries (FDI World Dental Federation, 2015)

Amongst the preventive measures for dental caries, the use of Fluoride is still considered the best protection against dental caries. In 2007, WHO's World Health Assembly passed resolution WHA 60/16 to enforce universal fluoride access for caries prevention as part of the basic right for human health (Khoshnevisan *et al.*, 2017). Fluoride is an essential nutrient involved in mineralization of teeth and bones. It especially plays important role in tooth remineralization and prevention of tooth decay (Iheozor-Ejiofor *et al.*, 2015).

Fluoride ingested through water has been found to have both positive (prevention of dental caries) as well as negative (dental fluorosis) effect on oral health. This has led to it being considered as a double-edged weapon (Anuradha *et al.*, 2011).

Dental fluorosis (DF) refers to changes in the appearance of tooth enamel that are caused by long-term ingestion of fluoride during the time teeth are forming (Aoba *et al*, 2002). Dental fluorosis is observed in specific geographical areas in the world showing an endemic epidemiological pattern affecting millions of people (Cintra-Viveiro and De la Fuente-Hernández, 2017). Research conducted in Australia showed that since the introduction of

community water fluoridation, 90% of children (12 years of age) had experienced dental fluorosis. This number however, in 1994 had reduced to 42.5% and in 1999, it reduced to 35.5% (Gussy *et al.*, 2008).

The occurrence of fluorosis (which was known as mottled enamel) in the primary dentition was first described in 1935 among children in Arizona (Warren *et al.*, 1999). In mild cases, chalky white opaque areas are observed, in moderate cases spots may be brownish, and in severe cases enamel is fragile which can lead to fracture and loss of tissue (Cintra-Viveiro and De la Fuente-Hernández, 2017)

However, dental caries prevalence (68.1%) was recorded in very high fluoride area (Sami *et al.*, 2015). In Malaysia, dental fluorosis prevalence was 46% while dental caries prevalence was 48% in water fluoridated area (Esa and Razak, 2001). Meyer-Leuckel *et al.* reported that ingestion of naturally fluoridated water in Iran seems to have a negligible effect on dental caries prevention but resulted in a high prevalence of dental fluorosis (Meyer-Lueckel *et al.*, 2006).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Dental caries, developmental defects of enamel and dental fluorosis are oral health problems of major concern to the population. The prevalence of these conditions has risen over the years. These conditions have direct effects on a small part of the body but its consequences are all-encompassing.

Some of the consequences include; difficulty with chewing, irritability, trouble with sleeping, school absenteeism as a result of pain, tooth loss, low self-esteem from tooth discoloration due to fluorosis or enamel defects, social anxiety, osteomyelitis, halitosis and even death in severe conditions.

These problems are more commonly seen in children who are the target population of this study.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

This study aimed at highlighting dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis among 9-year-olds of Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Knowledge of these defects on the surfaces of the teeth can help in planning proper community dental outreaches among residents of this local government area and its environs to educate them more regarding dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis.

This will also enable a proper assessment of its severity within that population for the above-stated age group so that proper distribution of resources to combat these conditions can be made. It will guide the government in decision making regarding whether more measures should be taken to increase or reduce or maintain fluoride concentration level in the community water supply within the area.

CHAPTER TWO

AIM, OBJECTIVES AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1 AIM

To determine factors associated with dental caries, developmental defects of enamel and dental fluorosis in 9-year-olds of Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

2.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To determine the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants.
- To determine the prevalence of dental caries, developmental defects of enamel and dental fluorosis among the study participants.
- To determine the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and the prevalence of dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis.
- To determine the relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis among the study participants.
- To determine the relationship between dental caries and developmental defects of enamel.
- To determine the relationship between developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis.

2.3 HYPOTHESIS

- H₀ – There is no relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and the prevalence of dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis.
- H₀ – There is no relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis among the study participants.
- H₀ – There is no relationship between dental caries and developmental defects of enamel among the study participants.

CHAPTER THREE

LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In performing this study, keywords were generated. These keywords were entered into the following databases: Google scholar, PubMed and Research Gate, abstracts and full papers of studies related to the research topic were read. After which the review was structured into three sections discussing: Dental caries, Developmental defects of the enamel (DDE) and Dental Fluorosis.

3.2 DENTAL CARIES

3.2.1 DEFINITION

Dental caries commonly referred to as tooth decay can be defined as a localized post-eruptive progressive pathological destruction of susceptible dental hard tissue that starts from the external surface of the tooth, leading to the formation of a cavity.

Dental caries is also the localized destruction of susceptible dental hard tissues by acidic by-products from bacterial fermentation of dietary carbohydrates (Pitts, 2018). It is a chronic disease that progresses slowly in most of the people (Selwitz *et al*, 2005) which results from an ecological imbalance in the equilibrium between tooth minerals and oral biofilms (plaque) (Nyvad, 2008).

The biofilm is characterized by microbial activity, resulting in fluctuations in plaque pH. This is a result of both bacterial acid production and buffering action from saliva and the surrounding tooth structure. The tooth surface is therefore in a dynamic equilibrium with its surrounding environment.

As the pH falls below a critical value, the demineralization of enamel, dentine or cementum occurs, while a gain of mineral (remineralization) occurs as the pH increases (Fejerskov O, 2004). The process of demineralization and remineralization takes place frequently during the

day. Over time, this process leads to either caries lesions or the repair and reversal of a lesion (Featherstone, 2004).

3.2.2 EPIDEMIOLOGY

Dental caries, one of the two commonest oral disease conditions contribute to the global burden of oral diseases and still constitute major public health concern in spite of an improvement in oral health. However, the disease is more prevalent in industrialized countries than in most 3rd world countries. (Akpata, 2004)

Prevalence: In most 3rd world countries, caries experience is higher in urban than in rural communities. It has also been observed to be on the increase. In contrast, caries experience is on the decline in many western countries possibly attributable to the use of fluoridated and improved oral health education (Rafael Moreira, 2012)

Research on dental caries in Nigeria has been conducted for several decades. The prevalence of caries in the early 1980s was high (Noah, 1981; Alakiya, 1983). However, the prevalence of dental caries varies with the study location in Nigeria ranging between 13.9% to 17.4% in the semi-urban settlement of Ile-Ife (Adekoya *et al.*, 2006; Ozegbo and Esan, 2013), to between 11.2% and 48.0% in urban areas such as Benin (Alakiya, 1983; Okoye *et al.*, 2010), Lagos (Giwa, 2005) and Ibadan (Denloye *et al.*, 2005).

The prevalence is higher in urban than in rural areas (Adegbembo *et al.*, 1995), higher in Northern than in Southern Nigeria (Akpata, 2004) and higher in primary dentition (2-3 years) than in permanent dentition (12years and above) (Akpata, 2004).

Sex difference: No sex differences in caries prevalence in studies conducted in Lagos (Sofola *et al.*, 2014), Enugu (Sowole *et al.*, 2007) and Ile-Ife (Adekoya *et al.*, 2006). Another study demonstrated that Females had a 43% reduced risk of having caries when compared to males (Denloye *et al.*, 2005).

Age difference: In Lagos, older adolescents had higher prevalence likewise in Enugu, the mean DMFT increased with age (Umesi-koleosho *et al.*, 2007), to corroborate this, another study revealed that the risk for early childhood caries increased by 7% for every month increase in age and the dmft increased by 0.01 with every month increase in the age of the child (Sowole *et al.*,

2007). A contrary finding however showed that the risk of having a dmft/DMFT equal to or higher than 3 reduced by 20% for every year increase in age (Folayan *et al*, 2010; Adeniyi *et al*, 2012).

Socioeconomic status (SES): The role of socioeconomic status in caries is less clear. Some studies show that in Lagos, the socioeconomic status had no influence caries experience (Folayan *et al* 2009). However for early childhood caries, the risk of caries increases by 23% as the SES decreases (Folayan *et al*, 2012). In Ile-Ife (Adekoya *et al*, 2006) and Ibadan (Poopola *et al*, 2013) however, the mean dmft/DMFT is highest in children from high social status.

3.2.3 AETIOLOGY

Dental caries results from interactions over time between bacteria that produce acid, a substrate that the bacteria can metabolize, and many host factors that include teeth and saliva. Dental caries results from an ecological imbalance in the physiological equilibrium between tooth minerals and oral microbial biofilms (Fejerskov O, 2004).

Bacteria live on teeth in micro colonies that are encapsulated in an organic matrix of polysaccharides, proteins, and DNA secreted by the cells, which provides protection from desiccation, host defences and predators and provides enhanced resistance to antimicrobial agents (Scheie *et al*, 2004). Teeth offer non-shedding surfaces for microbial colonization and large numbers of bacteria and their by-products accumulate in a biofilm on tooth surfaces in health and disease (Marsh P *et al*, 1999; Scheie *et al*, 2004).

The mechanisms of the caries process are similar for all types of caries. Endogenous bacteria (largely mutans streptococci [*Streptococcus mutans* and *Streptococcus sobrinus*] and *Lactobacillus* spp) in the biofilm produce weak organic acids as a by-product of the metabolism of fermentable carbohydrates. This acid causes local pH values to fall below a critical value resulting in demineralization of tooth tissues. If the diffusion of calcium, phosphate, and carbonate out of the tooth is allowed to continue, cavitation will eventually take place.

Demineralization can be reversed in its early stages through uptake of calcium, phosphate, and fluoride. Fluoride acts as a catalyst for the diffusion of calcium and phosphate into the tooth, which remineralizes the crystalline structures in the lesion. The rebuilt crystalline surfaces,

composed of fluoridated hydroxyapatite and fluorapatite, are much more resistant to acid attack than is the original structure. Bacterial enzymes can also be involved in the development of caries (Axelsson, 2000).

Whether dental caries progresses, stops, or reverses is dependent on a balance between demineralization and remineralization. The process of demineralization and remineralization takes place frequently during the day in most people. Over time this process will lead to either cavitation within the tooth or repair and reversal of the lesion, or maintenance of the status quo (Featherstone, 2004).

Remineralisation is frequent, especially when the biofilm pH is restored by saliva, which acts as a buffer. The remineralised areas have a higher concentration of fluoride and less microporous enamel structure than the original tooth structure because of the acquisition of calcium and phosphates from saliva. Caries lesions develop where oral biofilms are allowed to mature and remain on teeth for long periods. If a cavity is allowed to develop, the site provides an ecological niche in which plaque organisms gradually adapt to a reduced pH (Fejerskov, 2004).

Formation of a cavitated lesion protects the biofilm, and unless the patient is able to cleanse this area, the carious process will continue. Dental caries in enamel is typically first seen as white spot lesions, which are small areas of subsurface demineralisation beneath the dental plaque. Root-surface caries is similar to enamel caries, but unlike enamel caries, the surface can become softened, and bacteria penetrate further into the tissue at an earlier stage of lesion development (Fejerskov *et al*, 2003). A recession of the gingival margin, resulting from poor oral hygiene and loss of periodontal attachment with age, leads to exposure of the juncture of the crown with the root surface. This area retains dental plaque and is prone to developing carious lesions.

3.2.4 CLASSIFICATION

Dental caries may be classified according to the site of attack, extent, severity, the rate of progression and activity.

3.2.4.1 Classification according to the site of attack (Akpata *et al* 2013)

- a. Pit and fissure caries: Arises from the developmental irregularities. Most often on the occlusal surfaces of the posterior teeth.

- b. Smooth surface caries: These lesions occur on the smooth coronal surfaces of the teeth. The lesion usually starts from stagnation areas that are difficult for the patient to clean. The common surfaces involved are approximal surfaces, just below the contact area, as well as the cervical thirds of facial and lingual surfaces of all teeth
- c. Root caries: This involves the cementum often in the areas of gingival recession and is most commonly seen in elderly patients. The prevalence of root caries increases with the number of teeth retained until old age.

3.2.4.2 Classification according to the previous condition of a carious site (Akpata *et al* 2013)

- a. Primary caries: If the site of occurrence of a carious lesion was virgin (not previously restored), the lesion is described as primary caries, irrespective of its anatomic location, the rate of progression, extent or severity
- b. Secondary (recurrent) caries: This refers to the carious lesion which appears at the margins of restorations. It is most commonly seen at the cervical margins of restorations, particularly at the approximal surfaces.

3.2.4.3 Classification according to the extent of a carious lesion (Akpata *et al* 2013)

- a. Incipient caries: This is sometimes referred to as white spot lesion. The lesion is confined to enamel and is remineralizable. Only preventive management is required
- b. Advanced (dentinal) caries: This applies to a carious lesion that has penetrated the dentine. The lesion may be cavitated, and in extreme cases, the cusps may be broken down. Restorative measures are always required.

3.2.4.4 Classification according to severity (Akpata *et al* 2013)

- a) Rampant, acute, or severe caries: This form of caries spread fast and affects practically all teeth, including those normally resistant to caries attack. Such as the mandibular incisors. The condition is usually found in children but is rare in adults.
- b) Early childhood caries: This is a form of rampant caries marked by initial decalcification of the labial surfaces of the maxillary incisors. It occurs when the feeding bottle

containing sugary liquid food is left as a comforter for prolonged periods in the mouths of infants.

- c) Radiation caries: This is a form of rampant caries in which the salivary glands had been damaged as a result of irradiation of a tumor in the oral or perioral region. The consequent reduction in the salivary secretion deprives the dental plaque of the buffering action of saliva, and this results in increased caries activity.

3.2.4.5 Classification according to the rate of progression (Akpata *et al* 2013)

- a. Acute caries: Acute caries spreads very fast, destroying considerable tooth tissue. It is often seen in children.
- b. Chronic caries: This form of caries progresses very slowly and the lesion size may be relatively small. The lesion may be stained dark, with a leathery and firm consistency.
- c. Arrested caries: This form of caries occurs when the caries process is interrupted or has ceased to progress. It is usually characterized by demineralization and discoloration.

3.2.4.6 Blacks classification (Black, 1908)

Black classified carious cavities according to their sites of occurrence, and these are in plaque stagnation areas of the tooth.

Class I: These cavities occur in grooves, pits, and fissures. They can, therefore, be found in occlusal pits and fissures of molars and premolars groove on the buccal and lingual occlusal third of the molars, as well as the lingual pits of incisors and canine.

Class II: These occur on the approximal surfaces of molars and premolars.

Class III: These are found on the approximal surfaces of incisors and canines but do not involve the incisal angle.

Class IV: These occur on the approximal surfaces of incisors and canines and involve the incisal angle.

Class V: These occur on the facial or lingual surfaces of the cervical one-third of all teeth.

Class VI: This was recently used to describe cuspal caries.

3.2.5 CLINICAL PRESENTATION

The clinical presentation of dental caries varies, depending on their extent and location.

3.2.5.1 History

- Teeth sensitivity
- Toothache
- Bad breath
- Unpleasant taste in the mouth
- Inability to chew

3.2.5.2 Clinical Examination

- Brownish discoloration of pits and fissure
- Opacity beneath pits and fissure
- Frank cavitation of a tooth surface

3.2.6 INDICES FOR MEASUREMENT OF DENTAL CARIES

3.2.6.1 DMFT Index:

This is the decayed, missing and filled teeth due to caries index. It is a quantitative expression of a person's lifetime caries experience in the permanent teeth. It is frequently used as it is easy to use and does not require the use of sophisticated equipment. It gives a broad overview of caries experience in a population over a period of time. The D component gives tooth status affected by dental caries (caries morbidity). The M component gives tooth lost to dental caries (caries mortality). The F component gives the account of fillings done among the populations. There are two types. DMFT for permanent dentition and dmft for deciduous dentition. It is an effective tool for caries detection (Broadbent and Thomson, 2005)

3.2.6.2 DMFS Index:

When the DMFT index is employed to assess each individual surface of each tooth, it is termed as DMFS index. The principles, rules, and criteria for DMFS index is the same as that of DMFT index, only difference is that in DMFS index, surfaces are examined. This index is more precise and sensitive thus giving a true status of caries attack (Rozier, 1994)

3.2.7 PREVENTION

1) Oral hygiene:

Since dental caries do not progress without the bacteria present in dental plaques, daily plaque removal by brushing, flossing, and rinsing is one of the best ways to prevent dental caries and periodontal disease. Proper brushing and flossing methods may be taught at the dental office during routine check-ups.

2) Fluoride application:

Fluoride prevents dental caries by inhibiting demineralization of the crystal structures inside the tooth and enhancing remineralization. The remineralized surface is resistant to acid attack. In addition, fluoride inhibits bacterial enzymes (Featherstone, 1999). Methods of fluoride application include water fluoridation, fluoride tooth paste, fluoride mouth rinse, dietary fluoride supplements, and professionally applied fluoride compounds such as gels and varnishes.

3) Pit and fissure sealants:

The majority of dental caries in young children occur in pits and fissures. Pits and fissures are more susceptible to dental caries because the anatomy favors plaque accumulation; these areas are often too narrow for any oral hygiene measures to be effective. By filling such irregularities with flowable restorative material, the area becomes less morphologically susceptible (Beauchamp *et al*, 2008). This is especially recommended in young patients with erupting teeth and adults with a high caries index.

4) Xylitol:

Sucrose is a well-known cause of dental caries, and higher sucrose intake increases the risk of dental caries. However, it is impossible to eliminate sugar from the modern diet. Therefore, sugar substitutes have been developed to reduce caries risks. Xylitol is one of these sugar substitutes. Xylitol has a sweet flavor comparable to sugar, and it is not only non-cariogenic, but also anti-cariogenic. It keeps sucrose molecules from binding with MS, thereby blocking its metabolism. It also reduces the adhesion ability and number of MS (Trahan, 1995). The anti-cariogenicity of xylitol is affected more by the frequency of intake than by the amount consumed.

5) Vaccine:

As dental caries is an infectious microbiologic disease, there have been attempts to develop a vaccine. Some vaccines against MS in the form of proteins, recombinant or synthetic peptides, or protein-carbohydrate conjugates, as well as those based on DNA, have been successful experimentally, and an immune intervention can be undertaken by blocking the receptors which are necessary for the colonization of MS or by inactivating glucosyl transferases. However, none of these vaccines have appeared on the market thus far (Smith, 2012; Shanmugam KT *et al*, 2013) due to difficulty in inducing and maintaining high levels of antibodies in oral fluids; research is still ongoing for clinical applications.

6) Role of the primary caregiver in children:

As dental caries is an infectious disease, the primary caregiver of infants (most often the mother) can transmit caries-causing microorganisms to a child, resulting in the colonization of MS in the infant's oral cavity. In fact, there is a direct relationship between MS levels in parents and their children (Douglass *et al*, 2008). Therefore, efforts to reduce the MS level in the parent, including maintaining oral hygiene and undergoing dental treatment when necessary, are also important for prevention of dental caries in young children.

3.2.8 CONSEQUENCES

Dental caries frequently evokes aesthetic and functional complaints in teenagers thus affecting their quality of life. It has been observed that the greater the number of teeth affected or lost, the greater the negative effect on the patient's quality of life. The negative effects of dental caries on teenagers include: symptoms and functional alterations, such as chewing and speech

impairment, schooling factors, such as preschool absenteeism, psychological issues, such as trouble sleeping, and irritability, among other factors related to social interaction, such as smiling and refraining from speaking. School performance may also decline (Oliveira *et al*, 2008).

These effects are generally shown as a cumulative experience that worsens as the disease progresses, presenting oral clinical symptoms that indirectly affect the patient's quality of life. In more severe cases, caries may not only adversely influence the affected patient himself, but also interfere in his daily activities and those of others around him. A few studies have been conducted on children to assess how toothache caused by caries may impact their daily activities. Some authors have found that the most affected activities include eating meals and sleeping (Gift *et al*, 1992). It has also been estimated that sixty million school hours are lost each year due to tooth pain (Do and Spencer, 2007). Surveys measuring quality of life related to oral health in school children with dental caries show that life quality is strongly correlated with its negative impact on oral symptoms, followed by functional limitations and finally its impact on emotional and social well-being (Gift *et al*, 1992) .

Thus, dental treatment may offer a positive psychosocial impact on these patients, not only for recovering their oral health, but also for promoting an improvement of their quality of life.

3.3 DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF THE ENAMEL

3.3.1 DEFINITIONS

Developmental enamel defects are disturbances during enamel formation and may be manifested as enamel hypoplasia or opacities (Suckling, 1989). The opacities can either be diffuse or discrete.

Opacity is a hypo-mineralization defect involving alteration in the translucency of enamel and these opacities are white, cream, yellow, or brown in color (Seow *et al*, 2011).

Hypoplasia is a quantitative defect associated with a reduced or altered amount of enamel and appears as grooves and pits or else a partial or total lack of surface enamel (Martinez Gomez *et al*, 2012).

The developmental defects of the enamel (DDE) may be defined as the alteration of enamel that may affect an area of one surface or may be wide spread affecting all the surfaces throughout its full thickness. They may be quantitative in nature that is manifested as a deficiency in adequate thickness of enamel or qualitative in nature as enamel opacities (Wright, 2000).

3.3.2 EPIDEMIOLOGY

Several studies on the prevalence and severity of developmental defects of enamel (DDE) and associated risk factors have been undertaken in different parts of the world, but limited work in Nigeria has shown a range in prevalence of DDE, from 11% reported for 4- to 16-year-olds (Orenuga *et al*, 2010) to 23% reported for 12-year-olds (Koleosho, 2004) residing in 0.15-1.41 ppm F areas (Gbadebo, 2012). The actual prevalence and extent of DDEs can differ widely among different populations due to the relative impact of different aetiological and associated risk factors, but the reported prevalence of DDE also varies widely, in part because of the different terminologies and diagnostic criteria used in measurement indices.

3.3.3 AETIOLOGY

There are numerous hereditary, acquired, systemic and local aetiological factors which are associated with enamel defects. Since enamel does not remodel, the defects theoretically present a record of the insults suffered by the enamel organ during development of the enamel.

However, determining the specific timing of insults to the developing enamel is often difficult due to the current lack of knowledge regarding the chronology of the different stages of amelogenesis as well as individual variation in rates of enamel formation. (Seow, 1997; Lunt *et al*, 1974)

3.3.3.1 Hereditary Conditions

Enamel defects may be a presenting feature in hereditary conditions that involve only dental enamel or they may be a component of a generalized systemic syndrome. The inherited conditions which involve enamel only are known as amelogenesis imperfecta and the defects may present as enamel hypoplasia, hypomineralization or hypomaturation. Abnormalities of the genes involved in amelogenesis are primarily responsible for these defects (Witkop, 1988;

Wright JT *et al*, 2011). In children with amelogenesis imperfecta, characteristically, the teeth in both permanent and primary dentitions show DDE.

There are also many hereditary medical syndromes which may feature enamel hypoplasia. Enamel defects are often seen in Usher syndrome which is characterized by sensorineural hearing loss, retinitis pigmentosa and enamel hypoplasia (De La Pena *et al*, 2011) as well as in Seckel syndrome which features intellectual disability and multiple skeletal defects (Regen A *et al*, 2010). Ellis Van Creveld syndrome also show enamel hypoplasia together with defects of the skeletal and cardiac system (Nakatomi, 2009). DDE have also been associated with the Treacher-Collins syndrome, otodental syndrome, 22q11 deletion syndrome (also known as velocardiofacial syndrome) and Heimler syndrome.

3.3.3.2 Acquired Conditions

Numerous systemic or local acquired conditions that occur during the antenatal, perinatal or postnatal periods of development can also cause damage to developing enamel and result in DDE in the primary dentition. Prenatal conditions usually result in DDE which are located in the parts of the enamel formed before birth, while defects caused by postnatal disruptions are found in the parts formed after birth.

A common area for DDE in the primary dentition is the parts of enamel which mark the transition from intra-uterine to extra-uterine life, and separate the prenatally formed enamel from that which develops postnatally (Seow, 2005). This region, also known as the neonatal line, is present on the crowns of all primary teeth which commence mineralization prenatally (Skinner *et al* 1993). The presentation of the neonatal line varies from a mild change in direction of the enamel rods to a severe macroscopic defect extending into the dentine, depending on the degree of disruption experienced by the infant during the perinatal and neonatal periods.

Scanning electron microscopy studies of the neonatal line have demonstrated that it usually shows a less well organized enamel prism alignment, and has more organic material and less mineral content compared to the surrounding normal enamel. Thus, systemic disruptions occurring around the time of birth often result in exaggerated neonatal lines that are clinically visible as enamel hypoplasia in the primary dentition. Such conditions may be associated with

traumatic or preterm births, as well as metabolic or infectious conditions or environmental exposure to toxic chemicals.

Prenatal conditions which may be associated with enamel hypoplasia in the child include maternal vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy and neonatal tetany. Other antenatal factors which have been shown to contribute to enamel hypoplasia include maternal smoking during pregnancy, increased maternal weight gain during pregnancy and failure to access antenatal care. Multiple births are also a risk factor for DDE due to the higher rate of neonatal complications experienced by these children (Taji *et al*, 2011).

Although not commonly encountered in developed countries, nutritional deficiencies in the infant, particularly those associated with insufficient supply and absorption of vitamins A, C and D and calcium are well known to be risk factors for enamel hypoplasia in preterm and Indigenous communities. In addition, suboptimal nutrition stemming from extended breastfeeding without solid supplementation has also been suggested as a cause of DDE in primary teeth (Needleman *et al*, 1992).

Children born prematurely and those with low or very low birth weight have a higher prevalence of enamel hypoplasia compared to children born at full term with normal birth weights (Seow, 1989). DDE found in low birth weight and preterm children can be attributed to many adverse systemic conditions associated with premature birth, including respiratory disease, cardiovascular defects, gastrointestinal disturbances, haematological problems, immune deficiencies, intracranial haemorrhage, anaemia and renal defects.

Abnormalities associated with the mineralization pathways such as hypocalcaemia, osteopaenia, rickets and hyperbilirubinaemia have been directly implicated in the aetiology of DDE in the primary dentition (Seow, 1989). Deficient vitamin D metabolism, inadequate mineral levels and the inability of the gastrointestinal tract to absorb mineral are important contributors to the defective formation of dental enamel in preterm children due to immaturity of metabolic and mineralization systems. Furthermore, the risks of enamel hypoplasia from systemic conditions are often further compounded by local trauma from laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation which are often necessary in preterm children.

Besides prematurity of birth, coeliac disease is another condition where malabsorption and mineral deficiencies resulting from the gut enteropathy caused by gluten intolerance can cause DDE. Enamel defects are commonly encountered in coeliac disease to the extent that they have been proposed as a possible diagnostic sign of ‘silent’ coeliac disease in children (Majorana *et al*, 2010) electron microscopic analysis of hypoplastic teeth from children with coeliac disease has provided evidence that the enamel is less mineralized as well as more irregular in its organization. Renal and liver disease is also often associated with enamel hypoplasia, probably as a result of the mineralization pathways being disrupted in many types of renal and liver disease in children (Koch,1999).

Infectious diseases caused by bacteria and viruses such as infections of the urinary tract, otitis and upper respiratory disease have been associated with DDE. Although uncommon in developed countries, congenital syphilis acquired from maternal infections can cause enamel hypoplasia or ‘notching’ of the incisor teeth, and viral infections such as chicken pox, rubella, measles, mumps, and influenza have been associated with DDE in both primary and permanent dentitions, while cytomegalovirus (CMV) has been reported to cause enamel hypoplasia or hypocalcification in approximately one-third of affected infants. Enamel hypoplasia is also commonly present in children with cerebral palsy caused by maternal or foetal infection, foetal anoxia and hyperbilirubinaemia which are also risk factors for enamel hypoplasia. Thus, in many children with cerebral palsy, it is likely that the DDE commonly observed in the affected children are caused by the systemic disturbances which have damaged both the neurological and the enamel forming cells (Martínez *et al*, 2002).

Many chemicals and drugs have the potential to damage ameloblasts and cause DDE. Although there are few reports regarding the primary dentition, levels of fluoride greater than 1 ppm in the water have correlated with higher levels of DDE in the permanent dentition compared to fluoride levels of less than 1 ppm. Children with high lead levels from environmental exposure to lead paint, or accidental or pica ingestion have been reported to show enamel hypoplasia of the pitting variety. Tetracyclines have been well known to cause dental discolourations and enamel hypoplasia. More recently, amoxycillins have been implicated as a cause of enamel hypoplasia although it is often difficult to discount the effects of the fevers and infections which had required the use of the antibiotics (Hong *et al*, 2005).

Local factors such as trauma and infections have also been associated with enamel hypoplasia of the teeth in the immediate vicinity of the damage, in contrast to systemic factors which usually affect all developing teeth in the jaws. For example, trauma to the developing tooth germ, such as exerted through the laryngoscope or endotracheal intubation is known to cause damage to the ameloblasts, and result in opacities or hypoplasia in preterm children (Soew, 1997). In addition, demarcated markings which are commonly found on the labial surfaces of primary canines are also thought to result from local trauma exerted through the thin buccal cortical bone overlying the canines (Lukacs *et al*, 1995).

3.3.4 PATHOLOGY

The stage of amelogenesis at which time the dysfunction occurs, the severity of the insult leading to temporary, or permanent inactivity of the cells, the duration of the insult, the phase of ameloblast activity during the relevant period, and the specific agent involved, may affect the final appearance of the defect (Suckling, 1989). For example, damage of secretory ameloblasts results in pathologically thin enamel. However, interference during the maturation stage can lead to defects which present as bands, or patches of chalky opaque porous enamel (Moss *et al*, 1990). This is due to failure of the degradation and removal of some amino acid fractions; therefore, relatively large residues of organic material remain between the crystals. The presence of an organic ‘contaminant’ can retard or arrest further growth of the apatite crystals that are already present (Robinson *et al*, 1982).

Moreover, Hall (Suckling, 1980) claimed that some ameloblasts might subsequently recover from the insult during the maturation phase, which may account for the varying colour and degree of mineralization of the opacities that are known to occur. Different agents might initiate common pathways which lead to enamel defects with a similar appearance. Furthermore, based upon work on sheep, Suckling (Suckling, 1989) suggested that the pathogenesis of each type of DDE was different and therefore should be considered separately.

3.3.4.1 Pathology of demarcated/discrete opacities

The demarcated opacity is a defect which involves an alteration in the translucency and has a distinct and clear boundary with the adjacent normal enamel. The colour can be white, cream, yellow or brown. Demarcated opacities have been produced experimentally in sheep. This defect

followed trauma to cells in either the early or late maturation phase (Suckling, 1980), and after parasitic infection in the secretory or early maturation phases. Suckling claimed that yellow demarcated opacities resulted from an insult causing death of the ameloblasts early in their maturation stage while white demarcated opacities were found in sheep incisors following disturbances in the secretory, plus the early- and the late-maturation phases. Suckling also claimed that the yellow demarcated opacities that she induced often had a white opaque margin, which had a higher hardness value than normal enamel. This leads to the assumption that some maturation cells as well as secretory cells have the ability to recover (Suckling, 1989).

However, work on the teeth of humans and monkeys by Suga suggested that ameloblasts were very sensitive to disorders at an early stage of maturation. Hence, if a cell is damaged by a systemic or local disorder at this stage, it cannot easily recover from dysfunction during the long period of maturation. Therefore, he hypothesized that demarcated opacities were due to a disturbance in the process of matrix degradation, which originally occurs during the matrix formation stage, to provide suitable physiochemical conditions for the commencement of maturation.

In respect of the severity and duration of the insult, Suckling presumed that demarcated opacities were caused by a less severe, but longer lasting disturbance than that responsible for causing hypoplasia. Birgitta and Jörgen observed that the homologous teeth of children with demarcated opacities were affected to varying extents. However, they found it difficult to make any assumption about the severity of the insult because the damaging agent seemed to have been rather nonspecific in most of the children. Hence, they assumed that two or more interacting factors were required to produce the defects [Jälevik *et al*, 2000).

3.3.4.2 Pathology of diffuse opacities

Diffuse opacities also involve alterations in the translucency of enamel and are white in colour. They can have a linear, patchy or confluent distribution but there is no clear boundary with the adjacent normal enamel. Histologically diffuse opacities are subsurface-hypo mineralized defects covered by a well-mineralized outer enamel surface. It is believed that these defects result from a long, continuous low-grade insult. They have been produced in sheep by a daily low dose of fluoride for a period of six months (Suckling *et al*, 1988).

Diffuse opacities have been associated with an arrest in enamel maturation characterized by delayed breakdown of amelogenins which may become entrapped in the defective enamel. Moreover, data from a sheep study showed that the defects increased in severity when fluoride was also given during the secretory phase (Suckling, 1988). However, if the insult was confined to the secretory phase, then normal maturation occurred, resulting in translucent enamel even if the matrix was abnormal.

The effect of increasing the intake of fluoride during tooth development upon the appearance of the enamel has been well documented. Among the many hypotheses that have been proposed for the mechanism by which excess fluoride affects degradation and removal of enamel matrix proteins, three are favoured by most researchers:

- (i) Fluoride might directly affect ameloblasts (Denbesten *et al*, 1985).
- (ii) Proteins may be more tightly bound to fluoridated hydroxyapatite and, thus, proteinolysis might be more difficult (Tanabe *et al*, 1988).
- (iii) Fluoride might inhibit enamel proteinases (DenBesten *et al*, 1989).

However, there is no conclusive proof that fluoride alone, either in the form of an excessive intake, or of an abnormal metabolic process in the presence of a low or normal intake, is responsible for all the enamel changes of diffuse opacities. Other systemic factors operating over a long period of tooth development such as malnutrition, chronic illness (diabetes insipidus), or high altitude may mimic or augment the effects of fluoride. If the defects are true fluorosis, then it is an apt reminder that biological factors can enhance cellular responses to low concentrations of fluoride in the environment.

3.3.4.3 Pathology of Hypoplasia

Hypoplasia is a defect associated with a reduced quantity and hence thickness of enamel. Sarnat and Schour (Sarnat *et al*, 1941) believed that the morphologic unit of enamel hypoplasia was the enamel pit, which resulted from a cessation of ameloblastic activity. In a clinical investigation of anxious patients, whose childhood medical histories were available, it was concluded that a narrow zone of defect indicated a disturbance of short duration or an acute disease, while a wide zone indicated a disturbance of long duration or chronic disease.

More recently enamel hypoplasia has been produced in sheep by physical trauma (Suckling, 1980), by systemic illness induced by intestinal parasites (Suckling *et al*, 1983), and by a daily high dose of fluoride for a short period (Suckling, 1982). These findings indicate that hypoplastic defects are formed during the secretory phase of amelogenesis. The duration of the insult is relatively short, and it is the severity that determines the extent of the defect and the translucency of the partially formed enamel. The aetiology does not seem to be of major importance, since local and systemic factors result in defects with a similar appearance and physical characteristics.

3.3.5 CLINICAL PRESENTATION

Teeth affected by DDE can result in;

- 1) Compromised aesthetics due to staining and morphological alterations, children with DDE teeth may experience feelings of anxiety and social embarrassment (Rodd *et al*, 2011) regarding their dental appearance.
- 2) In many affected children there is increased dental sensitivity due to enamel hypomineralization and exposed dentine.
- 3) A higher prevalence of early childhood caries (ECC) in children with enamel hypoplasia. The correlation between DDE and ECC may be underestimated due to the presence of caries masking the underlying undiagnosed enamel defects (Johnsen *et al*, 1982).

The study of Mattee and co-workers which found that Tanzanian infants with enamel hypoplasia experienced more severe ECC in the absence of other risk factors such as inappropriate bottle feeding, use of sweetened pacifiers and cariogenic diets, suggesting that enamel defects is a significant risk factor for ECC. Mounting evidence for the increased caries risk from enamel hypoplasia in young children has led Caufield and co-workers to recently propose a new name, 'Severe, hypoplasia associated ECC' or HAS-ECC. The increased susceptibility of DDE affected teeth to caries is most likely due to the enamel defects

- 4) In addition to caries, the thinner and weaker hypoplastic or hypomineralized enamel predisposes the DDE teeth to tooth wear. Kazoullis and co-workers reported a strong association of dental erosion with enamel hypoplasia (Kazoullis *et al*, 2007). Seow and Taji proposed that

this is likely to be due to easy dissolution of hypomineralized teeth to ingested acids (Seow *et al*, 1986).

3.3.6 INDICES FOR MEASUREMENT OF DDE

MODIFIED DDE INDEX (Clarkson and O'Mullane, 1989)

	Code
Normal	0
Demarcated Opacity	1
Diffuse Opacity	2
Hypoplasia	3
Other defects	4
Combinations	
Demarcated and diffuse	5
Demarcated and hypoplasia	6
Diffuse and hypoplasia	7
All three defects	8

3.3.7 PREVENTION

Early diagnosis and preventive care are essential for the successful management of developmental enamel defects. Children who have a family history of amelogenesis imperfecta, or medical syndromes that are commonly associated with enamel defects such as epidermolysis bullosa or cerebral palsy or prematurity of birth should be assessed for enamel defects as soon as the teeth erupt. Also, as enamel formation of the permanent molars and incisors occurs at the same time as the primary molars, the presence of enamel defects in the primary molars indicates a risk for the defects occurring in the permanent dentition (Seow *et al*, 1986).

Thus, children with enamel defects in primary molars should have the permanent teeth monitored for the presence of similar defects. If both dentitions are affected, the possibility of a genetic cause should be considered, and the children referred to paediatric dentists and medical specialists for diagnosis, genetic testing and counselling.

3.3.8 CONSEQUENCES

Effects of DDE may include tooth sensitivity or an increased risk of caries. Treatment of DDE attempts to improve the function and appearance of the affected teeth (Wong *et al*, 2007). There is evidence that teeth with DDE have 10 times greater treatment need than normal teeth (Jälevik *et al*, 2002).

Apart from financial considerations of dental treatment, there is also the social cost including children's absence from school and parents' absence from work to attend multiple appointments. An affected individual may also experience low self-esteem or stigma because they perceive DDE as being disfiguring (Wondwossen *et al*, 2003).

The knowledge of aetiological factors for DDE is essential for clinicians when explaining and discussing the presence of DDE with patients and their parents. Targeting risk factors could also assist in implementation of community strategies to limit the occurrence of DDE.

3.4 DENTAL FLUOROSIS

3.4.1 DEFINITION

Dental fluorosis is a developmental disturbance of enamel, caused by successive exposures to high concentrations of fluoride during tooth development, leading to enamel with lower mineral content and increased porosity. The severity of dental fluorosis depends on when and for how long the overexposure to fluoride occurs, the individual response, weight, degree of physical activity, nutritional factors and bone growth, suggesting that similar dose of fluoride may lead to different levels of dental fluorosis (Den Besten, 1994).

Aesthetic changes in permanent dentition are the greatest concern in dental fluorosis, which are more prone to occur in children who are excessively exposed to fluoride between 20 and 30 months of age. It is also important to remind that the critical period to fluoride overexposure is between 1 and 4 years old, and the child would no bear risk around 8 years old (Rodriguez CRMD *et al*, 2002)

3.4.2 EPIDEMIOLOGY

Fluorosis is extremely common with 41% of adolescents having definite fluorosis and another 20% questionably having fluorosis according to the Centre for Disease Control (CDC). As at 2005, surveys conducted by the National Institute of Dental and Craniofacial Research in the USA (1986 to 1987) and Centre for Disease Control (1999 to 2004) are the only national sources of data concerning the prevalence of dental fluorosis. CDC however published an interim report covering data from 1999-2002 and it was reported that the prevalence of dental fluorosis was 43.15%.

Due to the universal presence of fluoride in water, soil and the atmosphere it is not surprising that humans are exposed to various levels of fluoride intake, not only through food and water, but in industrial and pharmaceutical products and other sources.

Epidemiological studies on fluorosis have been reported from various regions of the world including Africa (Alhoibeira *et al*, 2015), Saudi Arabia (Khan *et al*, 2001), India (Mishra *et al*, 2006), China (Peterson *et al*, 2006), Pakistan (Fooqi *et al*, 2007), Tanzania (Kaseva *et al*, 2006), Brazil (Casaprandia *et al*, 2007), Kenya (Gacir *et al*, 1993), Taiwan (Lung *et al*, 2008), Malawi (Msonda *et al*, 2001).

3.4.3 AETIOLOGY

Dental fluorosis is a specific disturbance of tooth formation caused by excessive intake of fluoride during the formative periods of the dentition. The severity and distribution of fluorosis depends on the concentration, duration of exposure to fluoride, the stage of ameloblast activity, and individual susceptibility.

Although, the mechanism by which fluoride causes fluorosis is not fully understood. It has been suggested that the fluoride interacts with the enamel forming cells (ameloblast) by influencing their ability to remove protein and water from the maturing enamel (Fejerskov *et al*, 1990). Other theories such as:

- 1) Fluoride interfering with the ameloblast's capacity to produce proteolytic enzymes necessary to initiate amelogenin break down.
- 2) Changes in cell morphology such as increased vacuolation due to the accumulation of unsecreted matrix (Robinson and Kirkham, 1990).

- 3) Increase in dermatan sulphate content may be an important detrimental factor (Sucheela *et al*, 1998).

A major cause of fluorosis is the inappropriate use of fluoride containing dental products such as toothpaste and mouth rinses. Sometimes, children enjoy the taste of fluoridated tooth paste so much that they swallow it instead of spitting it out. But there are other causes of fluorosis. For example, taking a higher-than-prescribed amount of a fluoride supplement during early childhood can cause it. So can taking a fluoride supplement when fluoridated drinking water or fluoride-fortified fruit juices and soft drinks already provide the right amount (Michael Friedman, 2017).

3.4.4 CLASSIFICATION/INDICES

Classification of dental fluorosis (Arathi Rao, 2012)

Direct inhibitory effect on enzymatic action of ameloblasts by fluoride leads to defective matrix formation and subsequent hypomineralization in case of fluorosis. The level of affectation has been classified and described in terms of it by various indices and this.

1. Dean's index
2. Thylstrup and Fejerskov scoring
3. Horowitz index

3.4.4.1 Dean's Index Score Criteria

Score 0 = Normal

Score 1 = Questionable with few flecks to occasional white spots

Score 2 = Very mild, small, opaque, paper white areas scattered irregularly, involving < 25%

Score 3 = Mild, involving < 50 %

Score 4 = Moderate - all the surfaces are involved with attrition and brown stain

Score 5 = Severe - discrete or confluent pitting and corroded appearance.

3.4.4.2 Thylstrup and Fejerskov Scoring Score Criteria

Score 0 = Normal translucency of enamel after prolonged drying

Score 1 = Narrow wide lines, corresponding to the perikymata

Score 2 = More pronounced lines, occasionally confluent

Score 3 = Merging and irregular cloudy areas

Score 4 = Entire surface is chalky white

Score 5 = Entire surface is opaque with pits that are < 2 mm in diameter

Score 6 = Regularly arranged pits forming horizontal bands with <2 mm vertical extension

Score 7 = Loss of outer most enamel with irregular surface not covering more than ½ of the surface

Score 8 = Loss of outer most enamel covering more than ½ the surface

Score 9 = Loss of main part of enamel with change in anatomic appearance of the tooth.

3.4.4.3 Horowitz Index Score Criteria

Score 0 = No visible evidence of fluorosis

Score 1 = Snow-capped tooth with areas of white extending up to the 1/3rd of the incisal edge and cusp tips

Score 2 = Extending more than 1/3rd but less than 2/3rd

Score 3 = Extending more than 2/3rd

Score 4 = Stains and any of the above

Score 5 = Discrete pitting without stain

Score 6 = Discrete pitting with stain

Score 7 = Confluent pitting and loss of enamel.

3.4.5 CLINICAL PRESENTATION

Symptoms/signs of fluorosis range from tiny white specks or streaks that may be unnoticeable to dark brown stains and rough, pitted enamel that is difficult to clean. Teeth that are unaffected by fluorosis are smooth and glossy.

3.4.6 PREVENTION

Dental fluorosis can be limited or prevented by following the ‘recommended limits for fluoride exposure’, suggested by US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). The reference dose suggested by USEPA is 0.06 mg fluoride/kg/day, which is the estimate of daily exposure that is likely to be without any appreciable risk of deleterious effects (any degrees of dental fluorosis) during a lifetime.

Specific guidelines for different ages were published by the US Food and Nutrition Board of The Institute of Medicine in 1997, recommending total daily fluoride intakes (Levy, 1995).

In this guideline, the suggested total daily exposure dosage for infants younger than 6 months of age of 0.01 mg fluoride/day in all drinks and food is lower than the USEPA recommended reference dose. These guidelines suggest greater attention should be given to the total fluoride intake of infants from water used to dilute infant formulas, foods and other supplement sources.

3.4.7 CONSEQUENCES

The moderate to severe form of dental fluorosis have an adverse cosmetic effect or an adverse health effect which has been the subject of debate for decades. Some early literature suggests that the clinical course of caries could be compromised by untreated severe enamel fluorosis. Smith and Smith, 1940 observed, “There is ample evidence that mottled teeth, thought to be somewhat more resistant to the onset of decay, are structurally weak, and that unfortunately when decay does set in, the result is often disastrous”

There appears to be general acceptance in today’s dental literature that enamel fluorosis is a toxic effect of fluoride intake that, in its severest forms, can produce adverse effects on dental health, such as tooth function and caries experience. For example:

- “The most severe forms of fluorosis manifest as heavily stained, pitted, and friable enamel that can result in loss of dental function” (Burtand Eklund, 1999).
- “In more severely fluorosed teeth, the enamel is pitted and discoloured and is prone to fracture and wear” (ATSDR, 2003).
- “The degree of porosity (hypermineralization) of such teeth results in a diminished physical strength of the enamel, and parts of the superficial enamel may break away... In the most severe forms of dental fluorosis, the extent and degree of porosity within the enamel are so severe that most of the outermost enamel will be chipped off immediately following eruption” (Fejerskov *et al.*1990).
- “With increasing severity, the subsurface enamel all along the tooth becomes increasingly porous... the more severe forms are subject to extensive mechanical breakdown of the surface” (Aoba and Fejerskov, 2002).
- “With more severe forms of fluorosis, caries risk increases because of piting and loss of the outer enamel” (Levy, 2003).
- “...the most severe forms of dental fluorosis might be more than a cosmetic defect if enough fluorotic enamel is fractured and lost to cause pain, adversely affect food choices, compromise chewing efficiency, and require complex dental treatment” (NRC, 1993).

3.5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DENTAL CARIES, DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF THE ENAMEL AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS

Dental caries increased with increasing severity of dental fluorosis, both in moderate- and high-fluoride areas. Thus, a positive relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis was observed across various tooth types, in both areas (Wondwossen *et al*, 2004). Also, a study by M Jain et al in 2009 among the Bhil tribes in India also showed the same results. However, in a 2009 study by Lida *et al*, they observed that molar teeth with fluorosis are more resistant to dental caries than molar teeth without fluorosis.

A 2015 study by Vargas-Ferreira et al identified a positive association between enamel defects and dental caries. The study concluded that a higher chance of dental caries should be expected

in individuals with developmental defects of the enamel. In the permanent dentition of children and teenagers, a positive association between enamel defects and dental caries was also identified (Farbiana Vargas *et al*, 2015).

3.6 LITERATURE MATRIX ON STUDIES OF DENTAL CARIES, DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS

AUTHOR	YEAR	LOCATI ON	SAM PLE SIZE	POPUL ATION STUDIE D	INDICES	SA MP LIN G	DATA COLLEC TION	DATA ANLYSI S	RESULTS
Olusola Ibiyemi <i>et al</i>	2017	Niger ia	322	8 year old	Modified DDE and Thylstrup and Fejerskov (TF) indices, DMFT/dm ft	Clus ter sam plin g	Clinical dental examinati on and Interviewe r administer ed questionai re	Kappa statistics, SPSS	Prevalence of DDE was 61.2% and a key predictor was history of infant/childhood disease, 29.8% of these exhibiting dental fluorosis.
Yadav P.K. <i>et al</i>	2015	Luck now, India	302	Pre- school children in rural and urban areas	Modified DED Dentition Status and treatment Need DMFT BMI	Mult istag e clust er sam plin g	Questionn aire Clinical examinati on	SPSS Chi- squared test Pearson correlati on	Enamel opacities found in 33.7% of underweight children. The mean DMFT was higher in underweight. Enamel opacities were more in

									subjects with >3 DMFT
N. Farsi <i>et al</i>	2010	Jedda h, saudi Arabi a	510	4-5 years	Modified DED index was used to describe dental defect, caries were described using DMFT	strati fied	Oral examinati on using a penlight, mouth mirror and a CPI probe		The prevalence of DDE of any type was 45.4% with that of demarcated opacities being the highest followed by hypoplasia. the mean DMFT is 3.9. A positive association between DDE and caries was observed
MEC El Frink <i>et al</i>	2008	Dut ch, nethe rland	386	5 years	Scoring criteria for molar incisor hypominer alisation. DMFS score	Strat ified	Dental examinati on was performed by 5 calibrated dentist in a dentist van	Chi square test	In 19 (4.9%) children a second primary molar was seen with a demarcated opacity
Janete May Baachiihal ente <i>et al</i>	2005	Hosp ital for rehab ilitati on of crani ofaci al anom alies, Baur u, Sao,	193 Boys, 119 Girls	3- 10years	Simplified hypoplasia index	strati fied	A single examiner carried out clinical examinati on under natural light with a dental probe and dental mirror and after drying the tooth		A prevalence of 43.8% was observed for unilateral and 39% for bilateral cleft. Cleft does not influence occurrence of hypoplasia.

		Brazil							
L. Pascie <i>et al</i>	1994	Australia	80	4-6 years	Modified DDE index	Stratified sampling	Oral examination using mirror and probe	Student's T-test and chi-square tests	79 of 80 children (99%) had enamel hypoplasia with a mean of 2.0, 4.1 hypoplastic teeth per child. Dental caries was noted in 66 (53%) of children and the mean number of decayed teeth was 3.9
L. Hong <i>et al</i>	2009	Iowa hospital, USA	698 (5 years old), 603 (age 9 years), 491 at both ages	5 years and 9 years	Modified D1-D3 version of the criteria of pitts and fyte	Stratified sampling	Parents were mailed and IFS questionnaire at 3-6 weeks intervals. The examination was conducted using a portable chair and halogen headlight. Teeth were evaluated using a mirror and without	Chi-square test, Wilcoxon two-sample test	Enamel hypoplasia was significantly associated with dental caries and it's a significant predictor for dental caries of childhood

							drying the teeth		
Yi Hond Li <i>et al</i>	1995	Haidan and Miyun, China	1344 children	3-5 years	Enamel defect score	Stratified sampling	Examination with or without cleaning		Enamel defect occurred more frequently on the buccal surface of teeth. Higher prevalence of teeth with defect in males compared to females. Children with low birth weight also showed a higher prevalence of enamel defect
Rebecca L. Slayton <i>et al</i>	2001	Iowa	698 children	4-5 years	Rusell's criteria	Stratified sampling	Oral examination without drying teeth	Percent agreement and keeper statistics. SPSS and SAS	There was no difference in the prevalence of enamel hypoplasia between boys and girls but significantly more boys than girls had enamel defects.
Al Rugg-Gunn <i>et al</i>	1998	Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	390 boys	2,4 and 6 years	DDE index	Stratified	Examination of the buccal surface of all the deciduous teeth	Multiple regression analysis	Malnutrition, low birth weight, childhood illness, brushing of child's teeth and swallowing toothpaste were related to the prevalence of developmental defects of deciduous teeth

Sandra Espindola Lunardelli, Marco Aurelio Peres	2003	Santa Catarina, Brazil	431 children	3-5 years	Modified DDE index	Systematic sampling	Total Examination with teeth cleaned and dried using gauze	Kappa statistics, chi-square test, Mann-willtrey U test	Approximately one-quarter of the preschool children presented with DDE in deciduous dentition and diffuse opacity most prevalent type of defect
Patricia correafaria <i>et al</i>	2016	Diamantina, Brazil	646 children	2-6yrs		Systematic sampling	Calibrated dental examiners performed the oral examinations	chi-square test and Poisson regression	Malocclusion and DDE did not cause a negative impact on the children's quality of life. Dental caries was associated with a negative impact on the quality of life of children. Malocclusion and DDE did not cause a negative impact on the children's quality of life.
Helen welton <i>et al</i>	2004	Republic of Ireland	17851	5,8,12,15	Dmft, Deans index	Random stratified sampling	WHO examination criteria		Prevalence of dental fluorosis is higher and caries incidence is lower in children and adolescent with fluoridated water supply
Anna lenasundel l <i>et al</i>	2015	Sweden	139	5 and 10 yrs	ICDAS	Stratified random sam	Examined by 2 calibrated examiners		Significantly higher prevalence of enamel defect In cleft lip and/ palate children of both age groups and

						plin g			anterior permanent teeth were mostly affected
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The literature matrix shows previous studies conducted between 2001 and 2017. Most of the studies in the table are carried out in Europe with study population size ranging from 139 to 1344. The age groups considered were between 5 and 10 years and indices used were DMFT, ICDAS (dental caries), Modified DED Index (DDE), Deans index (fluorosis).

3.7 RESEARCH GAPS

- Although there have been sporadic reports with regards to the prevalence of dental caries, DDE and dental fluorosis. However, no recent study has shown which is more prevalent amongst 9-year olds in Igbo-ora.
- There have been reports in dental literature concerning the relationship between dental caries, DDE and dental fluorosis. However, no recent study has been done on this amongst 9-year olds in Igbo-ora.

CHAPTER FOUR

METHODOLOGY

4.1 STUDY LOCATION

This study was carried out in Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government Area, Oyo State [Appendix 1]. Ibarapa Central LGA is one of the eleven Local Governments located in Oyo State with its headquarters situated at Igboora. Approximately 92,000 (National Population Census 2006) people reside there. Igboora has seven wards namely; Ward 4 (Iberekodo I and villages), Ward 5 (Iberekodo II and villages), Ward 6 (Idofin and Saganun villages), Ward 7 (Pako and villages), Ward 8 (Isale oba and villages), Ward 9 (Oke-Iserin and villages, Ward 10 (Oke-Odo and villages).

The residents are majorly artisans and traders and pride themselves in having about 3 major markets where trading activities are carried out. Igboora provides efficient and quality infrastructure for effective education training, it boasts of numerous Nursery, Primary and Secondary schools which are overseen by the Local Government Supervisory Councillor for Education and officer in charge of the Local Government Educational Authority. A Tertiary Institution named- Oyo State College of Agriculture and Technology is also located in Igboora.

4.2 STUDY DESIGN

The study is a cross-sectional study with a study period extending from January 14 to February 8, 2019.

4.3 STUDY POPULATION

Participants in the study included children aged 9-year-old, comprising both male and female.

4.4 SAMPLE SIZE ESTIMATION/DETERMINATION

Our sample size was determined using the Kish Leslie (1965) formula for population lesser than 10,000

$$n = \frac{z^2pq}{e^2}$$

$$d^2$$

Where:

n = desired sample size

z = standard deviation, usually 1.96

p = proportion of the target population (prevalence)

q = 1 – p

d = degree of accuracy (0.05)

The prevalence that was used in the formula was obtained from a previous study. It was from a study conducted in 2010, in Awgu North Local Government in Enugu State, Nigeria. The prevalence of Dental Caries in a Nigerian Rural Community showed a prevalence of 33%.

Therefore prevalence (P) value = 33 %.

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.33 \times 0.67}{0.05^2} = 340 \text{ participants}$$

Hence, a total of 340 was determined as the sample size. However, in order to make room for attrition (participants who may refuse to continue participating in the study) a 10% addition was made, which gives a sample size of 340 + 34 = **374** participants. However, **378** 9-year olds participated in the study.

4.5 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

A multistage sampling technique was implemented, in which 1 school in each of the 7 wards in Igboora community was randomly selected by balloting. The number of students in 7 schools chosen was obtained from the enrolment data from the Local Government Education Authority. The total number of students from the 7 schools was used in determining the number of participants per school by utilizing the proportional sampling method.

$$\text{Hence: } X \left[\text{Percentage of participants} \right] = \frac{\text{number of students in each school} \times 100}{\text{Total number of students from 7 schools}}$$

from each school

Total number of students in the 7 school

$$\text{Number of participants per school} = \frac{X \times 378}{100}$$

The number of classes with the corresponding sample population (9-year-olds) was obtained from the head-teacher and the number of respective arms were noted. The arms in which the study was done was chosen by balloting. Cluster randomization method was used in selecting the study participants.

4.6. PERMISSION AND ETHICAL APPROVAL

4.6.1 PERMISSION

Permission to carry out the study was obtained from the Ministry of Education, the Local Government Authority and the Headmaster and Headmistress of the schools. Informed consent was obtained from legal guardians and parents of the students, assent was also obtained from the participants.

4.6.2 ETHICAL APPROVAL

Researchers underwent a training which was certified by the Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI). Evidence of certification was submitted to the Head of the Community Dentistry Unit who read the proposal into details and permission to undertake the study was obtained from the Local Inspector of Education of Ibarapa Central LGA and the Headmaster/Headmistress of each school.

The study was carried out in compliance with the following:

- **Beneficence:** The study benefitted all the study participant in that Oral Health Instructions and Motivation was administered prior data collection.
- **Do no harm:** The study did not cause any form of harm to the study participants.
- **Fairness and justice:** The study was carried out without bias.

- Confidentiality of data collection was ensured in that names of the participants was not written and data collected was stored in lockers that was only accessible by researchers.
- The study was voluntary, undertaken without any coercion and participants were free to withdraw at any time without harm.

4.7 PREPARATION FOR DATA COLLECTION

4.7.1 PROCUREMENT OF RESEARCH MATERIALS:

In order to aid an easy and effective means of data collection, certain materials were procured which played a crucial role. These materials included: wooden spatula, facemask, cotton wool swabs, gloves, weighing scale, metre rule and sample bottles.

4.7.2 GENERATION OF CLINICAL ASSESSMENT FORM AND QUESTIONNAIRE

4.7.2.1 ORAL HEALTH ASSESSMENT FORM

The assessment form was generated using the World Health Organisation (WHO) Oral Health Assessment as a guide

4.7.2.2 QUESTIONNAIRE

The semi-structured questionnaire was generated after reading literatures and consulting experts in the Community Dentistry Unit. The prepared questionnaires are in the English language, hence translation into the Yoruba language was carried out because certain participants were only able to understand the Yoruba language with the original meaning of the question(s) preserved.

4.8 DATA COLLECTION

This was done in 3 phases.

4.8.1 PHASE 1 (ORAL EXAMINATION)

Examination of the oral cavity was done under natural light using: wooden spatula, dry cotton wool pellets, disposable gloves and facemask. The oral cavity of the participant was examined for Dental Caries, Developmental Defects of Enamel and Dental Fluorosis using the

DMFT/dmft, modified DDE index of the buccal surface of each tooth and Dean's score respectively. The examination sheet is shown in appendix 2.

4.8.2 PHASE 2 (INTERVIEW)

Information about the history of pregnancy, history of delivery, childhood illnesses, dietary and tooth cleaning practices using an interviewer administered (semi-structured) questionnaire as seen in appendix 3.

4.8.3 PHASE 3 (SAMPLE COLLECTION)

A well labelled universal bottle comprising the identification and school number of the participant was used. This was given to each participant to collect a sample of drinking water consumed in their homes and schools which will be assessed for fluoride concentration.

4.9 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY:

4.9.1 ORAL EXAMINATION

Training and calibration was done prior to the definitive study under the supervision of a trained examiner.

4.9.2 QUESTIONNAIRE

Pre-testing was done in Idere, a community having similar social, cultural and environmental conditions as Ibarapa Central Local Government.

4.9.3 DRINKING WATER

New universal bottles were used, legal guardians and parents were instructed to rinse the bottles with the source thoroughly before collecting the actual sample.

4.10 DATA MANAGEMENT

- a) **Data cleaning:** The data collected was properly checked daily to ensure that there was no error of omission and commission. Any error observed was corrected immediately.
- b) **Data handling:** Data was coded and recoded.
- c) **Validity of Coding:** Cross-checking of the code with 5% of the data.

- d) **Generating data sheet:** Using the codes.
- e) **Data entry:** The data was first entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet before it was exported into SPSS.
- f) **Data analysis:** Was done using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20. Frequencies, means (SD) and diagrams (bar charts, pie charts and histogram) were generated. Association between categorical variables was done using chi-square test while association between continuous variables was done using student t-test at $p < 0.05$.

4.11 DISSEMINATION

Findings from the study was disseminated to inhabitants of Ibarapa Central Local Government, Oyo State through research to policy feedback programme, with a presentation to the Faculty of Dentistry and at International and Local conferences.

4.12 GANTT CHART

S/N	Activity	Person(s)	Duration
1.	Literature review	All members	1day
2.	Proposal writing	All members	2days
3.	Proposal presentation	All members	1day
4.	Printing of proposal and questionnaire	All members	1day
5.	Procurement of materials	All members	1 day
6.	Arrival and tour	All members	1 day
7	Courtesy visit and permission	All members	1 day
8.	Data collection	All members	14 days
9.	Data collection and analysis	All members	7days
10.	Analysis and presentation	All members	5days

4.13 RESEARCH BUDGET

S/N	ITEM	JUSTIFICATION	PER UNIT PRICE(₦)	QUANTITY	AMOUNT(₦)
1	Questionnaires	To collect relevant data.	20	374	7480
2	Wooden spatula	For oral examination.	1200	1.5 packs	1530
3	Facemask	Universal precaution.	330	1 pack	330
4	Conform gloves	Universal precaution.	100	3packs	300
5	Refreshment	-	200	6	1200
6	Cotton wool	For cleaning the teeth surface.		0.5 pack	535
7	Incentives	To stimulate co-operation of the participants.	21.30	300	6390
8	Universal bottles	To collect water samples		374	40,000
8	Miscellaneous (5%)				2480
				TOTAL(₦)	60,245

CHAPTER FIVE

RESULTS

5.1 RESPONSE RATE

All 378 pupils that were recruited agreed to participate in the study. Response rate for oral examination was 100% but only 152 (43.8%) parents/legal guardians responded to the questionnaires.

5.2 SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Table 5.1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of study participants. The age of study participants was 9 years. One hundred and ninety-two (50.8%) of the study participants were males while one hundred and eighty-six (49.2%) were females. Eighteen participants (4.8%) were in Basic 1, eleven (2.9%) in Basic 2, two hundred and sixty-one (69%) in Basic 3, fifty three (14%) in Basic 4 and thirty five participants (9.3%) were in Basic 5.

The majority, one hundred and forty-nine (98%) of the participants were Yorubas while the rest were non-Yorubas. Seventy-one fathers (46.7%) reported their highest level of education as primary while seventy-nine mothers (52.0%) also had their highest level of education as primary.

Forty eight of the study participants (31.6%) were from middle socio-economic class while one hundred and four (68.4%) were from low socio-economic class.

Table 5.1: Socio Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Demographic Characteristics	No	%
Gender (n=378)		
Male	192	50.8
Female	186	49.2
Class (n=378)		
Basic 1	18	4.8
Basic 2	11	2.9
Basic 3	261	69
Basic 4	53	14
Basic 5	35	9.3
Ethnicity (n=152)		
Yoruba	149	98
Other tribes (Hausa, Igbo)	3	2
Father's level of education (n=152)		
None	10	6.6
Primary	71	46.7
Secondary	55	36.2
Tertiary	16	10.5
Mother's level of education (n=152)		
None	17	11.2
Primary	79	52
Secondary	42	27.6
Tertiary	14	9.2
Socio-economic class (n=152)		
Middle socio-economic class	48	31.6
Low socio-economic class	104	68.4

5.3 PREVALENCE AND PATTERN OF DENTAL CARIES.

On clinical examination, 13 (3.4%) of the participants had at least one carious lesion (**Table 5.2**). The mean (\pm SD) dmft and DMFT scores were 0.12 (\pm 0.536) and 0.05 (\pm 0.322) respectively. The occurrence of dental caries was higher among females with 8 of them having at least one carious lesion (**Table 5.4**). The majority of the participants with carious lesions (n=6) were from Basic 3 (**Table 5.3**).

There was no statistical significance relating the occurrence of dental caries with the gender of the participant or the socioeconomic class of their parents.

Table 5.2: Participants with carious lesions

PARTICIPANTS WITH CARIOUS LESIONS			
		Frequency	Percentage (%)
	Teeth without caries	365	96.6
	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	13	3.4
	Total	378	100.0

Table 5.3: Classes of participants with carious lesions

CLASS OF THE PARTICIPANTS VS CARIOUS LESIONS (p >0.05)				
		Carious lesions		Total
		Teeth without caries	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	
Class	Basic 1	17	1	18
	Basic 2	10	1	11
	Basic 3	255	6	261
	Basic 4	52	1	53
	Basic 5	31	4	35
Total		365	13	378

Table 5.4: Gender of participants with carious lesions

GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS VS CARIOUS LESION (p>0.05)				
		Carious lesions		Total
		Teeth without caries	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	
Gender	Male	187	5	192
	Female	178	8	186
Total		365	13	378

Table 5.5: Socioeconomic class of participants with carious lesions

SOCIOECONOMIC CLASS OF PARTICIPANTS VS CARIOUS LESIONS (p>0.05)				
		Carious lesions		Total
		Teeth without caries	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	
Socioeconomic class	Middle Socioeconomic Class	45	3	48
	Low Socioeconomic Class	100	4	104
Total		145	7	152

5.4 PREVALENCE AND PATTERN OF DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF THE ENAMEL.

On clinical examination using the modified DDE index, 151 (39.9%) of the participants had at least one tooth with DDE (**Table 5.6**). The occurrence of DDE was higher among the male participants with majority of them (n=89) having at least a tooth with DDE (**Table 5.8**). The majority of the participants with DDE (n=98) were from Basic 3 (**Table 5.7**).

There was no statistical significance relating the occurrence of DDE with the gender of the participant or the socioeconomic class of their parents.

Table 5.6: Participants with DDE

PARTICIPANTS WITH DDE			
		Frequency (n)=378	Percentage (%)
	Participants with all teeth normal	227	60.1
	Participants with at least 1 DDE	151	39.9

Table 5.7: Classes of participants with DDE

CLASS OF PARTICIPANTS VS DDE (p>0.05)				
		DDE		Total
		All teeth normal	Teeth with at least 1 DDE	
Class	Basic 1	10	8	18
	Basic 2	8	3	11
	Basic 3	163	98	261
	Basic 4	29	24	53
	Basic 5	17	18	35
Total		227	151	378

Table 5.8: Gender of participants with DDE

GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS VS DDE (p>0.05)				
		DDE		Total
		All teeth normal	Teeth with at least 1 DDE	
Gender	Male	103	89	192
	Female	124	62	186
Total		227	151	378

Table 5.9: Socioeconomic class of participants with DDE

SOCIOECONOMIC CLASS VS DDE (p>0.05)				
		DDE		Total
		All teeth normal	Teeth with at least 1 DDE	
Socioeconomic class	Middle Socioeconomic Class	27	21	48
	Low Socioeconomic Class	64	40	104
Total		91	61	152

5.5 PREVALENCE AND PATTERN OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS.

On clinical examination using the Dean's index, 156 (41.3%) of the participants had at least one tooth with dental fluorosis (**Table 5.10**). The occurrence of dental fluorosis was higher among the male participants with majority of them (n=88) having at least a tooth with dental fluorosis (**Table 5.13**). The majority of the participants with dental fluorosis (n=102) were from Basic 3 (**Table 5.12**).

There was no statistical significance relating the occurrence of dental fluorosis with the gender of the participant or the socioeconomic class of their parents.

Table 5.10: Participants with dental fluorosis

PARTICIPANTS WITH DENTAL FLUOROSIS			
		Frequency	Percentage (%)
	All teeth normal	222	58.7
	At least one tooth with fluorosis	156	41.3
	Total	378	100.0

Table 5.11: Dean's score

Dean's score for dental fluorosis			
		Frequency (n)=378	Valid Percent
	Normal	222	58.7
	Questionable	67	17.7
	Very mild	43	11.4
	Mild	22	5.8
	Moderate	21	5.6
	Severe	3	0.8

Table 5.12: Classes of participants with dental fluorosis

CLASS OF PARTICIPANTS VS DENTAL FLUOROSIS (p>0.05)
--

		Dental fluorosis		Total
		All teeth normal	At least one tooth with fluorosis	
Class	Basic 1	10	8	18
	Basic 2	8	3	11
	Basic 3	159	102	261
	Basic 4	28	25	53
	Basic 5	17	18	35
Total		222	156	378

Table 5.13: Gender of participants with dental fluorosis

GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS VS DENTAL FLUOROSIS (p>0.05)				
		Dental fluorosis		Total
		All teeth normal	At least one tooth with fluorosis	
Gender	Male	104	88	192
	Female	118	68	186
Total		222	156	378

Table 5.14: Socioeconomic class of participants with dental fluorosis

SOCIOECONOMIC CLASS VS DENTAL FLUOROSIS (p>0.05)				
		Dental fluorosis		Total
		All teeth normal	At least one tooth with fluorosis	
Socioeconomic class	Middle Socioeconomic Class	27	21	48
	Low Socioeconomic Class	64	40	104
Total		91	61	152

5.6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DENTAL FLUOROSIS AND DENTAL CARIES.

As shown in table **5.15**, 6 participants (1.58%) who had dental caries also showed some degree of dental fluorosis. However, 7 of the participants (1.85%) who had dental caries did not have dental fluorosis.

There was no statistical significance relating dental fluorosis to dental caries in our study.

Table 5.15: Relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis

DENTAL FLUOROSIS VS DENTAL CARIES (p=0.716)				
		Dental caries		Total
		Teeth without caries	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	
Dental fluorosis	All teeth normal	215	7	222
	At least one tooth with fluorosis	150	6	156
Total		365	13	378

5.7 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DENTAL CARIES AND DDE.

As shown in table 5.16, 6 participants (1.58%) who had dental caries also had DDE. However, 7 of the participants (1.85%) who had dental caries did not have DDE.

There was no statistical significance relating dental caries to DDE in our study.

Table 5.16: Relationship between dental caries and DDE.

DENTAL CARIES VS DDE (p=0.642)				
		DDE		Total
		All teeth normal	Teeth with at least 1 DDE	
Dental caries	Teeth without caries	220	145	365
	Teeth with at least 1 carious lesion	7	6	13
Total		227	151	378

5.8 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DDE AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS.

As shown in table 5.17, 142 participants (37.5%) who had DDE also had dental fluorosis. However, 9 of the participants (2.38%) who had DDE did not have dental fluorosis.

There was a statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) relating DDE and dental fluorosis in our study.

Table 5.17: Relationship between DDE and dental fluorosis.

DDE VS DENTAL FLUOROSIS (p<0.05)				
		Dental fluorosis		Total
		All teeth normal	Teeth with at least 1 dental fluorosis	
DDE	All teeth normal	213	14	227
	At least one tooth with DDE	9	142	151
Total		222	156	378

CHAPTER SIX

6.1 DISCUSSION

Dental caries (which can result from developmental defects of the enamel) is a disease process resulting in the demineralisation of dental hard tissues by microbial activity. It is a readily preventable disease and can be arrested or reversed in its early stages (Kidd et al, 1997).

Developmental defects of the enamel (DDE) have been defined as disturbances in hard tissue matrices and their mineralization that arise during odontogenesis. DDEs have been regarded by some authors as the main risk factors for dental caries even though its nature has not been identified and its cause is not clear (Salanitri et al, 2013). Amongst the preventive measures for dental caries, the use of Fluoride is still considered the best protection against dental caries. However fluoride ingested through water has been found to have both positive (prevention of dental caries) as well as negative (dental fluorosis) effect on oral health. This has led to it being considered as a double-edged weapon (Anuradha *et al*, 2011).

Our study was carried out in Ibarapa Central Local Government Area which is a rural region within Igboora, Oyo State, Nigeria. In our study, the prevalence of dental caries was low (3%) which is in agreement with a similar study done in rural communities in South West Nigeria in 2018 where a dental caries prevalence of 12.2% was reported (Akinyamoju et al, 2018).

However the low prevalence in our study is in contrast to a similar study done in Awgu North Local government Area (rural community within Enugu, Nigeria) in 2010 where dental caries prevalence of 33% was reported (Okoye and Ekwueme, 2011).

The prevalence of dental caries was higher in females (2%) than in males (1.3%) this is similar to the study earlier stated which was done in Agwu North Local Government Area in Enugu state where caries was more amongst females. In our study (n=152), 4 participants from the low socioeconomic class had carious lesions which is similar to a study done by Denloye et al where incidence was reported to be lower amongst low socioeconomic class (Denloye et al, 2013).

The low prevalence of dental caries (3%) in our study, can be attributed to the fact that majority of our study participants consume non-cariogenic diet (77%) while those who consume cariogenic diet are (8.6%). Also, our study revealed that a significant proportion of the study

participants had dental fluorosis which earlier studies have suggested could be protective of dental caries (Lida *et al*, 2009).

The respondents generally had a low mean dmft score of 0.12(\pm 0.536) and DMFT of 0.05 (\pm 0.322) which is in contrast to a study done in North Central Nigeria where the mean score was 0.69 (\pm 1.2).

The prevalence of DDE in our study was 39.9% which is in contrast to a study done in rural areas of Oyo state, Nigeria which was found to be 61.2% (Ibiyemi *et al*, 2017). This was due to the history of infant/childhood disease that was a key predictor in that study unlike in this study in which history of infant/childhood disease was found to be insignificant with DDE. In our study, more males were found to have DDE than females which is similar to a study done in Ile-Ife Nigeria (Folayan *et al*, 2014). In our study, most of the individuals who had DDE also had dental fluorosis. Showing a significance between DDE and dental fluorosis.

In this study, the prevalence of dental fluorosis was high (41%) which is in contrast to a study done in Oloibiri, Bayelsa State with a prevalence of 18%. The high prevalence of dental fluorosis in our study suggests that most of the school children residing within the region are exposed to high amounts of fluoride. Fluoride concentration in their drinking water will be assessed to confirm this. Age, sex, ethnicity and socioeconomic class had no statistical association with the prevalence of dental fluorosis. From our study, we could hypothesize that the high level of dental fluorosis (41%) is responsible also for the low prevalence of dental caries (3%).

In our study there was a significant relationship between DDE and dental fluorosis ($p < 0.05$) similar to a study done in Iran which had a $p = 0.001$ (Sabokseir *et al*, 2016). There was no significant relationship between DDE and dental caries ($p > 0.05$) and no relationship between dental caries and dental fluorosis ($p > 0.05$) which is in contrast to a study in Ethiopia which evaluated the association between dental caries and dental fluorosis ($p < 0.05$).

6.2 CONCLUSION

The prevalence of dental caries amongst 9-year olds of Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government, Oyo State was low (3%). This shows that dental caries is not a public health problem in the community. However the prevalence of DDE and dental fluorosis were high

(40% and 41% respectively). This implies that both conditions require public health interventions and the levels of fluoride consumption in the community should be monitored.

6.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **To The Individuals:** Efforts should be made by individuals to acquire basic knowledge about good oral hygiene practices. Regular dental visits should form an integral part of routine general health check-ups. Individuals are encouraged to seek more information about dental caries, dental fluorosis and DDEs in order to know how to prevent its occurrence.
2. **To The Government/Policy Makers:** Improved access to primary healthcare, raising the socioeconomic status of women through skill acquisition and non-formal education has been shown to impact positively on health seeking behaviours. The curriculum of schools should be reviewed to include basic oral health education and remedies for dental health problems. Cost of treatment for oral health diseases should be subsidized to encourage good utilization of available dental services.
3. **To The Parents:** Children should be motivated to carry out proper oral hygiene practices. Parents should desist from self-medication and treatment, they should rather be encouraged to visit the nearest dental clinic routinely and whenever there is any oral condition that requires treatment.
4. **To The Community:** Priority should be placed on proper dental care. Awareness programs on major oral health problems should be welcomed and encouraged by the community.
5. **To The Oral Health Practitioners:** Oral health practitioners should embark on community awareness programs that will improve the knowledge of the community regarding dental caries, dental fluorosis and DDEs.
6. **For Future Research:** Future research should be carried out in similar communities to monitor the prevalence of dental caries, dental fluorosis and DDEs in Nigeria.

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1

MAP OF IGBOORA, IBARAPA CENTRAL LGA, OYO STATE

APPENDIX 2

ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENT AND DENTAL HEALTH ASSESSMENT FORM

Area code:

Child identification number:

Height :..... (cm)

Weight :.....(Kg)

Tooth type (Primary)		55	54	53	52	51	61	62	63	64	65	
dmft												
DDE												
Tooth type (Permanent)	16	15	14	13	12	11	21	22	23	24	25	26
DMFT												
DDE												
DDE												
DMFT												
Tooth type (Permanent)	46	45	44	43	42	41	31	32	33	34	35	36
DDE												
dmft												
Tooth type (Primary)		85	84	83	82	81	71	72	73	74	75	

Dean's Score for Dental Fluorosis:

(considering the labial/buccal surfaces of ALL erupted teeth)

Dmft/DMFT: ALL ERUPTED TEETH

*DDE: Buccal surfaces of 10 index teeth.

APPENDIX 3

QUESTIONNAIRE

DENTAL CARIES, DEVELOPMENTAL DEFECTS OF THE ENAMEL AND DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN 9-YEAR-OLDS OF IGBOORA, IBARAPA CENTRAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT OYO STATE.

Serial Number _____

Dear Respondent,

We are final year dental students of the College of Medicine, University of Ibadan conducting a study on dental caries, developmental defects of the enamel and dental fluorosis among 9-year-olds of Igboora, Ibarapa Central Local Government, Oyo State. It is purely for academic purposes and your participation and full cooperation in answering these questions will be highly appreciated. Be aware that your participation in this study is voluntary and you can opt out at any point if you feel uncomfortable. All information provided will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Thank you for your anticipated cooperation.

Having understood the content and reason for this study, I willingly agree to take part.

Signature of Respondent: _____

Date: _____

SECTION A

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

1. Age of child _____
2. Gender (1) Male (2)Female
3. Tribe _____
4. Has your child been living in this locality since birth? Yes No
If no, for how long? _____
5. Father's level of education
None
Primary
Secondary
Tertiary
6. Mother's level of education

- None
- Primary
- Secondary
- Tertiary

7. Father's Occupation _____
8. Mother's Occupation _____
9. Father's Income(N) Daily _____ Weekly _____ Monthly _____
10. Mother's Income(N) Daily _____ Weekly _____ Monthly _____

SECTION B

PREGNANCY HISTORY

1. Were you ill during pregnancy? Yes No I don't know
 If yes, which month were you mostly ill? _____
2. Which drugs did you mostly use? _____
3. Did you use herbal concoctions during pregnancy? Yes No I don't know
 If yes, what month did you consume it mostly? _____
4. Was there an incidence of trauma to the foetus during pregnancy? Yes No
5. When you were pregnant, did you change diet? Yes No
6. Did you receive ante-natal care? Yes No
7. Did you receive immunization during pregnancy? Yes No

SECTION C

DELIVERY HISTORY

1. Where was the child delivered? _____
2. What type of delivery? _____
3. What was the gestation age at delivery? _____
4. Was your child big or small at delivery? _____
5. Was the delivery eventful or uneventful for the child? Yes No
 If yes, specify _____

SECTION D

CHILDHOOD ILLNESSES

6. While growing up, did your child ever fall sick? Yes No
7. If yes, did the child have any of the following?
- Whooping cough Malaria Neonatal tetanus Rheumatic fever
- Measles Asthma Diarrhea Chickenpox
- Trauma to the face Trauma to the teeth others (specify) _____
8. From the list above, which disease did the child have the most? _____
- At what age? _____
9. Which drugs did your child use? _____

SECTION E

DIETARY PRACTICE

1. Was your child exclusively breastfed? Yes No
2. If yes to question 1, did you breastfeed your child through the night? Yes No
3. If yes to question 1, at what age did you stop? _____
4. If yes to question 1, what type of food was mostly used to wean? _____
5. Was your child exclusively formula fed? _____
6. If yes to question 5, at what age did you stop? _____
7. If yes to question 5, what type of diet was mostly introduced? _____
8. Was your child mixed-fed? ? Yes No
9. If yes to question 8, what type of food was mostly used to wean? _____
10. If yes to question 8, at what age did you stop? _____
11. Did you bottle feed your child with sugary diet? ? Yes No

12. If yes to question 8, what time of the day did you bottle feed your child? _____
13. If yes to question 8, when did you start bottle feeding your child? _____
14. If yes to question 8, when did you stop bottle feeding your child? _____
15. What type of food was mostly used to wean your child? _____
16. What type of drink was mostly used to wean your child? _____
17. List the type of food mostly consumed by your child at present? _____
18. List the type of snack mostly consumed by your child at present? _____

SECTION F

TOOTH CLEANING

1. At what age did you start cleaning your child's teeth? _____
2. What do you use to clean your child's teeth? (a) Cotton wool and toothpaste (b) Toothbrush and toothpaste (c) Cotton wool only d. Others (specify) _____
3. If your child uses toothpaste, what brand of toothpaste?(a)Oral B (b) Maclean (c) Close up (d) Dabur (e) Others (specify) _____
4. If your child uses toothpaste, select the amount used in the figure below.

5. How many times do you clean your child's teeth in a day? _____

6. After cleaning your child's teeth, does your child (a) Spit and rinse (b) Spit only (c) Rinse only